

PERFORMANCE OF PRICES OF MAJOR SPICES TRADED AT NCDEX, MUMBAI

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Abstract

The research focuses on the analysis of the performance of Dhaniya, Jeera, and Turmeric traded at the National Commodity & Derivatives Exchange (NCDEX) in India. The study highlights the importance of futures markets in stabilizing prices, managing risks, and facilitating price discovery for these agricultural commodities. The research examines data from 2015-2023, analyzing daily closing spot and futures prices for the selected spices. Using statistical tools such as Compound Growth Rate (CGR) and Coefficient of Variation (CV), the study provides a comprehensive overview of market volatility and price trends. The compound growth rates for Dhaniya were 0.004 for spot price, 0.01 for future price, and -0.86 for delivered quantity, indicating slight growth in prices but a decline in delivery performance. For Jeera, the spot price had a CGR of -0.60 while the future price showed a significant positive growth of 0.67, with delivery contracts declining at -0.26. Turmeric demonstrated a slight negative growth in spot price at -0.13, with the future price showing marginal growth at 0.18 and delivery rates declining sharply at -1.17. Price volatility was evaluated using the Coefficient of Variation (CV) and Cuddy Della Index, showing moderate variability in spot and future prices but higher variability in delivery performance for all three commodities. The regression coefficients for Dhaniya, Jeera, and Turmeric indicated no statistically significant impact of factors like area and production on spot prices at AGMARK and NCDEX. For instance, the regression coefficient for area in Jeera was -0.60 with a t-value of 5.16, and the coefficient for production in Turmeric was 2.63 with a t-value of 0.71, neither showing significant impacts on market prices.

Keywords: NCDEX, Dhaniya, Jeera, Turmeric, Spot price, Future price, Delivered quantity, Compound Growth Rate (CGR), Coefficient of Variation (CV), Cuddy Della Index, Price volatility.

Introduction

Crops play a major role in the economic development and prosperity of many countries. Farmers (sellers) and business owners (buyers) began to contract to exchange their products for future cash. This is how the "futures market" contract evolved, where the producer agreed to sell his product (wheat) to the buyer the next day at an agreed price. This way the farmer knew in advance that he would be paid and the business owner knew the costs involved. This arrangement is considered to be beneficial for both sellers and buyers. Contracts were noisy and started changing hands even before the delivery date. Equity futures in India are almost similar to stock futures in the United States. The first futures market in India was the Bombay Cotton Trade Association Limited, which was established in 1875. Oilseed futures trading began in 1900 with the establishment of the Gujarati Vyapari Mandali. Gold futures started in Bombay in 1920. Future business. Most of these licensed products are traded through various stock exchanges in India. The Indian economy is directly and indirectly dependent on agricultural products. Agricultural business already has a share and with future business in National Products stock exchange it will provide more products, find cost and provide better risk management. Now, National Products The. Stock exchange also invites new investors to find new businesses and have different businesses. The National Commodity Futures Exchange was supposed to provide price discovery, better investment and better risk management. Considering the significant future of the Indian economy, this study has a broad objective to analyze the performance of the agricultural products market in India on the commodity exchange.

Methodology

The present study was conducted with respect to National Commodity and Derivatives Exchange Ltd (NCDEX) Mumbai which started trading in November 2003. For the present study, three major agricultural commodities currently traded in the commodity exchanges were selected. They were Dhaniya, Jeera, Turmeric. These crops were selected based on their volume of trade in respective commodity

Table 1 : Compound Growth Rate of Dhaniya in NCDEX (2015 – 2023)

Sr.No	Particular	Compound Growth Rate	t value
1	Spot price	0.004*	0.04
2	Future price	0.01*	0.07

exchanges. Secondary data on futures price, spot prices, and volume, value of trade on exchanges were collected from the official website of National Commodity and Derivatives Exchange Ltd (NCDEX) Mumbai for the period 2015-16 to 2022-23

Analytical tool

For the purpose of accomplishing the objectives, which is to study the prices and quantities traded through NCDEX data were analyzed using the following techniques

Compound Growth Rate Estimation

$$y = ab^t \text{ (1)}$$

Where:

- **y** is the dependent variable, representing the prices or quantities traded through NCDEX.
- **a** is the intercept, which acts as a constant in the model.
- **b** is the regression coefficient, representing the growth factor.
- **t** is the time variable, indicating the period over which growth is measured.

To facilitate estimation, Equation (1) is transformed into a linear form by taking the logarithm of both sides:

$$\text{Log } Y = \text{Log } a + \text{Log } b \text{ (2)}$$

This transformation linearizes the equation, making it suitable for regression analysis. Once the regression was performed, the percent annual compound growth trend is computed using the following relationship:

$$\text{CGR} = [\text{Antilog}(\log(b)) - 1] \times 100 \text{ (3)}$$

This formula calculates the CGR, which indicates the average annual rate of growth over the study period. The significance of the regression coefficient will be tested using the t-test, which determines whether the observed growth rate is statistically significant.

Result and Discussion

For achieving the first objective, which is to study the prices and quantities traded through NCDEX, the Compound Growth Rate (CGR) was calculated using a regression model. The fundamental equation for estimating CGR is:

3	Delivery	-0.86***	-2.61
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Note

*** Significant at 1 per cent (Table t value is 2.581)

** Significant at 5 per cent (Table t value is 1.962)

*Significant at 10 per cent (Table t value is 1.646)

It is evident from the table that the Compound Growth Rate (CGR) for spot and future prices of the commodity is positive, showing marginal growth of 0.004% and 0.01%, respectively, with low significance. However, delivery performance shows a significant negative CGR of -0.86%, indicating a decline.

For **Dhaniya**, the data shows more stability, especially in the spot and futures markets. The CGR for the spot price remains neutral at 0.004, indicating no growth or decline, with a T value of 0.04 reflecting stable

price levels. Similarly, the future price exhibits very slight positive growth, with a CGR of 0.01 and a T value of 0.07 showing little difference from the spot price, further reinforcing the stability of the market. However, like Turmeric and Jeera, delivery contracts are underperforming, with a CGR of -0.86 and a relatively lower T value of -2.61 suggesting weaker performance in delivery compared to spot and futures markets.

Table 2 : Compound Growth Rate of Jeera in NCDEX (2015 – 2023)

Sr. No	Particular	Compound Growth Rate	t value
1	Spot price	-0.60***	5.16
2	Future price	0.67***	5.04
3	Delivery	-0.26*	0.69

Note

*** Significant at 1 per cent (Table t value is 2.581)

** Significant at 5 per cent (Table t value is 1.962)

* Significant at 10 per cent (Table t value is 1.646)

The table reveals that while the spot price experienced a significant decline with a Compound Growth Rate (CGR) of -0.60%, the future price showed strong positive growth at 0.67%, both with high significance. However, delivery recorded a minor negative CGR of -0.26%, indicating slight underperformance.

For **Jeera**, the data presents a volatile market with sharp contrasts across categories. The spot price has experienced a substantial decline, as evidenced by the CGR of -0.60, yet the T value of 5.16 remains quite

high, suggesting that despite the negative growth, prices are still elevated. Conversely, the future price shows strong growth with a CGR of 0.67, pointing to a bullish outlook, supported by a T value of 5.04 which remains just below the spot price. Delivery performance is relatively weak, with a CGR of -0.26 and a low T value of 0.69 indicating that delivery contracts for Jeera are not performing well compared to the other categories.

Table 3: Compound Growth Rate of Turmeric in NCDEX (2015 – 2023)

Sr. No	Particular	Compound Growth Rate	t value
1	Spot price	-0.13*	1.11
2	Future price	0.18*	1.57
3	Delivery	-1.17*	-1.81

Note

*** Significant at 1 per cent (Table t value is 2.581)

** Significant at 5 per cent (Table t value is 1.962)

* Significant at 10 per cent (Table t value is 1.646)

The table indicates that both spot and future prices showed marginal growth trends, with a Compound Growth Rate (CGR) of -0.13% and 0.18%, respectively, though with low significance. Delivery, however, saw a notable decline with a CGR of -1.17%, reflecting a significant drop in performance.

For **Turmeric**, the CGR data at NCDEX reveals mixed performance across different categories. The spot price has a slightly negative CGR of -0.13, indicating a mild decline, with a T value of 1.11 reflecting a moderate price level. In contrast, the future price shows a positive CGR of 0.18, suggesting optimism in the futures market, although the T value of 1.57 is slightly lower than the spot price. Delivery, however, shows a significant underperformance, with a CGR of -1.17 and a much lower T value of -1.81 indicating substantial weakness in delivery contracts for Turmeric.

Conclusion

In comparison to the spot market, the futures market is better at accurately reflecting new information to prices. Therefore, it is concluded that the futures market is crucial to the process of determining prices for the three commodities we chose, making it valuable for both buyers and sellers of the commodities in the spot and futures markets

Futures vs. Spot Prices: The study highlights that futures prices are more reflective of market expectations compared to spot prices. Futures markets have proven effective in managing price risk, allowing

traders and farmers to hedge against price fluctuations, thereby ensuring more predictable income streams.

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